

STAGES AND TAXONOMY OF DEVELOPMENT STUDENTS'
COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE BASED ON A REFLECTIVE
APPROACH

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Abstract. This article discusses the role of the reflexive approach in developing students' communicative competence, the use of reflexive and communicative taxonomy in teaching English, and creative thinking skills based on the reflective approach.

Key words: reflexive approach, student, general secondary school, taxonomy, language, communication, skill, communicative competence, English language.

Language is the primary means of communication, relations between people around the world and establishing good relations between countries. In the modern world, the English language stands out from other languages as it is used by so many people living in different states, countries and regions. Today, English is used in many fields such as economics, medicine, journalism, education, business, science, technology and mass media, pharmacology, and is considered as the leading language in which scientific research is conducted in these fields. Also, in many developed countries, higher education is conducted in English, and a number of the most important modern books can be read only in English. It is widely used in Internet networks and business relationships, which are an integral part of the modern world.

The Reflexive and Communicative Taxonomy in English Language Teaching is a general vocabulary for teachers to think about educational goals and consists of the following components (Figure 1):

Levels of cognitive processes	the essence of the learner (key verbs)	Examples of questions based on the taksonomy
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can the learner retrieve or recall information from memory? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognizes, remembers, names, describes, repeats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who, what, where, when, how..? What ...? It iis correct, isn't it?

To help determine the level of critical thinking for a task, American psychologist Benjamin Bloom developed a method for classifying the different levels of critical thinking skills required in a classroom setting. In the 1950s, his taxonomy was interpreted as a common purpose for all teachers to think about educational goals.

Table 1

LEVELS OF REFLECTIVE AND COMMUNICATIVE TAXONOMY

<p>KNOWLEDGE OR RECALL</p>	<p>At the Knowledge level, questions are asked only to check that the student has received specific information from the lesson.</p>
<p>COMPREHENSION</p>	<p>The Comprehension level makes students to remember facts and understand information instead. At this level they can interpret the facts.</p>
<p>APPLICATION</p>	<p>Practical questions require students to apply or use what they have learned. They may be required to</p>

	solve problems with the information they receive in class to create viable solutions.
ANALYSIS	At the analysis level, students need to go beyond knowledge and skills and see information they can use to analyze a problem.
EVALUATION	In this stage, students must evaluate the information and conclude whether the information the author may present is correct or incorrect.
CREATION	At this last stage, the student should create things independently using the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities.

There are six levels in the taxonomy, each of which requires a higher level of abstraction from students. The teacher should try to move the students to the taxonomy. Unfortunately, tests written only to assess knowledge are very common. However, it is important to incorporate higher levels into lesson plans and tests to create thinkers, not rote learners.

What should be considered when implementing reflexive and communicative taxonomy?

There are many reasons why teachers use the levels of the reflexive and communicative taxonomy. For example, a teacher can design a task by checking the taxonomy to ensure that different skill sets are required for different students,

and using it in lesson preparation helps the teacher to ensure that all levels of critical thinking are needed throughout the lesson will help.

Many of the tasks developed with the Reflective and Communicative Taxonomy could be more specific, such as tasks aimed at developing critical thinking skills that all students need for real life. Of course, teachers recognize that it is much easier to assess tasks developed at lower levels (knowledge, program) of the taxonomy than at higher levels. In fact, the higher the taxonomy level, the more complex the classification. For more complex assignments, with analysis, synthesis, and evaluation-based assignments, headings are essential to ensure fair and accurate assessment.

Educators with a reflexive approach express ideas that other educators do not think of, choose a unique style of expression, sometimes ask unrelated or unusual questions, enjoy open-ended questions, discuss ideas based on clear evidence. prefers an unconventional approach to problem solving. A reflexive approach requires continuous research from educators. The analysis of scientific literature allows to distinguish the structural components of the reflexive approach that are interrelated. It is necessary to pay attention to the creation of a communicative environment in the development of communicative competences in children based on a reflexive approach.

In the reflexive approach, personal communicative qualities are listed as follows: creativity in communication, ability to think logically, erudition (maturity), rich imagination, creative effectiveness and initiative in communication, full demonstration of creativity in communication, ability to reflect, all forms of emotions, ability to take risks.

Creative thinking skills based on a reflexive approach are interpreted as follows:

1. Fluency. The ability to come up with many ideas. It is based on the word "many".

2. Flexibility. The skill of coming up with different ideas is based on the word "change".

3. Uniqueness. Think of an idea that stands out from others. This is based on the word "unique".

4. Creativity. The skill of expanding ideas is based on the word "adding".

In organizing the process of creative thinking, which is considered the main principle of the reflexive approach in developing students' communicative competence, the English teacher should provide interesting and complex tasks with clear goals and time, realize that creativity creates a feeling of imbalance, and get rid of anxiety and fear. It is supposed to help to develop creative thinking skills with other skills, not to "rescue", but to guide. Also, providing English teachers with constructive comments and introducing them to new instructions will increase the effectiveness of reflexive and communicative teaching in English classes.

The ability of English language teachers to develop other types of reflexive and communicative skills is important in creating an environment that will be the foundation for them to be able to work in a group, to have emotional freedom and positive thoughts.

The teacher's strict adherence to the principle of creativity (creative approach) during training is a factor in achieving the expected result. It is important to provide students with a system of guiding questions and tasks that allow them to self-control, analyze and evaluate their activities consciously, creatively and independently.

This has been called the 'Reflexive and Communicative Taxonomy' and it can be used to study topics in English textbooks as follows:

1. Why should I study this topic?
2. What does knowing it give me?

3. I need to determine the connections, similarities and differences with the knowledge and information I have learned before (in previous topics).

4. How do I draw conclusions from this person (story)?

5. What achievements and shortcomings have I understood?

6. What practical communication skills have I acquired?

In this way, the training in a certain sense begins to become a problem-based education and approaches the practice of the method of forming reflexive competencies proposed by O.S. Anisimov in the system of problem-based education.

Any knowledge, skills and experiences related to children's independent study are first formed during the lessons. Even the beginning of habituation to independent study and the process of becoming a way of life directly depends on the lessons. A child who did not enjoy reading the lesson materials and did not participate in their analysis will not have the desire to study independently, and as a result, the possibility of attracting him/her to this type of study will disappear. Independent study cannot be forced: otherwise, it is not independent, but forced education. When a child is aesthetically satisfied with communicative interaction through lessons, a reflexive need for reading arises. In order to meet this need, he wants to communicate in English independently. Based on this, reflexive skills are first formed during class activities, and this is gradually transferred to the process of independent study. The most common and effective way to develop these skills is dialogues. In the center of dialogues there are mainly questions and tasks performed through these questions or separate from them.

Questions and tasks are considered necessary for the teacher to guide students towards the goal. Depending on the age of the child, they can be slightly different - simplified or complicated. For example, in the 5th grade, children cannot ask the questions in the above-mentioned "reflexive and communicative taxonomy" by themselves, but they understand through the teacher's questions and even

explanations. For example, in the 5th grade "What does Kiara want to be?" In the text called "Winter" festival in Russia, brief information is given. It will be more effective to explain this text to children using "reflexive and communicative taxonomy" questions. To gain knowledge about the "Winter" festival from the text, to explain the educational significance of the fact that a Russian girl named Kiara wants to participate in the Russian national festival and goes to a dance club to fulfill this dream, to be able to use the words given in the text in the audience, comparing and analyzing with our festivals, drawing conclusions from Kiara's enthusiasm, demonstrating what communication skills the students have, recognizing their shortcomings and achievements. It is better to leave the answers to the last questions to the children themselves, who at this age will express their opinion based on the text or draw conclusions from it.

Also, students' communicative competence such as being able to communicate, understand and express sources within the context of the content of the text is developed by using the short sentences given in the 6th grade textbook to explain the questions of "reflexive and communicative taxonomy".

"Why should I study this subject?" The question allows you to check whether the students have remembered the words and content of the texts. The text begins to unfold in the reader's mind, and after mastering the text, it is explained to bring out the purpose implied in the question. Questions based on the content of the text like "Why do you need to know them?" by the teacher are asked, students' opinions are heard, any answer, regardless of whether it is logical or not, is heard to the end, encouraged, and discussed accordingly. Answers should not be complex and wordy. Talking about the similarities and differences of the text with our national traditions develops students' comparative thinking, which is one of the factors of forming reflexive skills.

In the 5th and 6th grades, more attention is paid to the independent approach of students to the system of questions and assignments. Because certain experience

and skills that have started to form during two years leave their creative mark on the child, of course. Before studying the text given in the textbooks, it is recommended to conduct an introductory conversation, in which the teacher can use exhibitions, as well as seen and read TV shows, newspapers, magazines, and books. Students will also be able to add some other important fact if they know it.

Students are asked to ask themselves questions from the "Reflexive and Communicative Taxonomy", and each child is asked to think about the answer, and then share ideas with the classmate next to them. One of the children in several pairs gives information by comparing his/her own and his/her partner's views on this matter. A representative of several other couples also express their views in this way. Then the teacher asks: "Look, you got acquainted with the thoughts and views of your classmates, tell me, which classmate's opinion do you think is better than yours?" Why?". There are two merits in asking the question in this way: firstly, the calming down the feeling of to show off, characteristic of 5th-6th grade students, who involuntarily look for and mentally observe that they were able to show a strong argument among their classmates and compares the answers. This is a special "cunning" method of the teacher: in order to show yourself, you need to find someone superior to yourself!

Secondly, one of the most important indicators of reflexive skills is self-critical evaluation, and another indicator is having comparative thinking, as well as striving for independence of activity (mental, observational activity) which stimulates the development of skills. At the same time, as noted in the article of scientist N. Khalilova, these assignments have a special role in the objective assessment of the results and the level of opportunities of one's work, and the development of reflexive thinking.

Pupils get acquainted with the text of a story in the form and method deemed acceptable by the teacher. But first, the teacher should tell the additional information that the students want to know during the introductory interview.

When completing the third task in "Reflexive and Communicative Taxonomy", students are again offered the practice of free activity and independent thinking. Children remember information about the topic based on the knowledge they have acquired in previous topics. Previous topics, children can find points of connection to several topics studied in lower grades. Of course, conducting the analysis in the form of exchange of opinions, discussion and competition will increase the effectiveness of the training.

The fourth task involves looking at oneself, taking into account and analyzing the information based on the knowledge and impressions they received from the lesson. It also teaches students to evaluate themselves and draw conclusions for the near and distant future. Approximately, most students will have harmonious answers to the following points: My conclusion is that I will learn more from now until I am older; I will be the best specialist in my profession and work; I will successfully finish everything I started; whatever I do, my efforts, knowledge, and work should benefit the people and ease their burden. As an achievement, I can say that I learn many languages and use them effectively. I have a lot of shortcomings: when I get addicted to the game, I forget about other things, even my studies; sometimes my cheerfulness stops me, so I don't get to the end of what I started; Today I realized that I do some actions for myself, I don't think about others, I don't listen, etc.

In short, if this method is consistently used, the formation of reflexive skills will emerge before the teacher's eyes when studying the given educational materials. In this case, a student who knows the sequence of activities well is inclined to independent movement, free speech and activity; strives to take a leading role in the processes of analyzing educational activities and assimilating new information; has a high level of training and motivation, develops comparison through abstract thinking; most importantly, the ability to self-evaluate and correct is formed.

References

1. Havighurst R. Human Development and Education // David McKay, New York 1953. – p. 312.
2. Weinert F. Handbuch der Kompetenzmessung // Schäffer Poeschel, 2003. – p.524.
3. Анисимов О.С. Субъектная рефлексия в игромоделировании и ее понятийное обеспечение. – М.: Угрешская типография, 2012. – С. 285.
4. Файзуллаева Н. Диалог в педагогической культуре учителя. Электрон манба: https://ibris-nbuu.ua-cgiirbis_64.
5. Пьянкова Г.С. Рефлексивные методы организации самостоятельной работы студентов: учебное пособие / Краснояр. гос. пед. ун-т им. В.П.Астафьева. – Красноярск, 2015. – 189 с.

